

INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS - THE FOUNDATION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.

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Annotation: The article highlights the main ways of development of the national economy of Uzbekistan, identifies the most important priority areas of creation, introduction of innovations and new technologies. The role of the development of national scientific policy and its reform is also revealed.

Keywords: innovation, priority, technology, innovation potential.

In Uzbekistan, close attention is paid to stimulating research and innovation activities, creating effective mechanisms for introducing scientific and innovative achievements into practice, organizing scientific and experimental specialized laboratories, high-tech centers, and technoparks at higher educational institutions and research institutes. [1]

We have set an ambitious goal - to become one of the 50 leading countries of the world by 2030 according to the rating of the Global Innovation Index. In 2021, work was carried out to increase the scientific and innovative potential of the regions. So, together with the Ministry of Innovation, regional (committees) of the khokimiyats, based on the needs of the population and the real sector of the region's economy, hold competitions for financing scientific and innovative projects. And the relevant Presidential Decree of April 1, 2021 approved the list of districts being transformed into innovation zones in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and regions. [2]

In our opinion, in order to achieve high results in science, it is necessary to clearly define priorities. To this end, in the next five years, research will be conducted in the following areas in the field of science:

First. Creation of new technologies for the treatment of infectious diseases, oncology, cardiology and phthysiology based on the mechanism of the state order for scientific research. At least 20 percent of the budget allocated for the development of science will be directed to scientific research in the field of healthcare.

Second. The development of "green" technologies, the transition to low-carbon energy technologies, cyclic resource-saving and renewable energy technologies, agricultural technologies aimed at reducing the carbon dioxide content in the air. Research in this area will become the basis for the transition to a "green" economy. At least ten percent of the budget allocated to science will be allocated for these purposes.

The third. Management of production processes of artificial intelligence technologies in science, development of effective methods and means of their application in medicine, pharmaceuticals and agriculture.

Fourth. Creation of technologies aimed at ensuring food security, including the development of new standards and methods, value-added processing technologies, technologies for the development of export-oriented organic agricultural products. At least 15 percent of the funds are planned to be allocated to scientific projects in this area.[8]

In our opinion, international cooperation has always been and remains among the priorities of our activities. After all, it serves as an important element of success in education and science. So, to the infusion Currently, cooperation has been established with such authoritative international structures as the World Bank, the Islamic Development Bank, the UN, UNESCO, and others.

Today there are 32 active projects supported by the World Bank in the country. Their total cost is more than \$ 4.6 billion. In addition, 12 more initiatives worth over \$1.7 billion are under development. All of them make a certain contribution to the implementation of important economic reforms, the development of agriculture, water supply, energy, transport, healthcare, education, science and innovation, social protection systems, modernization of urban and rural infrastructure, as well as mitigation of the consequences of COVID-19.[8]

Another important milestone in the development of Uzbekistan's international relations in the field of science and education was the beginning of cooperation with UNESCO. Thus, over the past few years, the education sector of the UNESCO Representation in Uzbekistan has developed a number of resources, manuals and manuals on such aspects as "Development and assessment of competence in the field of information and communication technologies", "Guidance for teachers on the prevention of violence and bullying in schools", "Guidance on gender review of textbooks", "Guidance to develop the potential of teachers in the field of classroom teaching, taking into account a gender-oriented approach." At the same time, UNESCO provides assistance to the organization's

member States in investing in science, technology and innovation, as well as in developing national scientific policies and reforming their scientific systems.

Today, intergovernmental and international agreements are in force with China, Russia, India, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and CIS member countries, as well as with Great Britain, Hungary, Germany, South Korea, the USA, Turkey, Japan. In total, more than 94.6 billion soums have been allocated to support 117 international research projects in cooperation with these countries. They cover such areas as artificial intelligence and genetic engineering, agriculture and technology. [7]

The announcement of the startup project competition is carried out at least twice a year. This serves to stimulate youth initiatives, support novice scientists and developers. As of December 2021, 56 rounds of competitive selection of projects (fundamental, applied, innovative) on various topics were held.

In order to introduce venture financing and attract financial resources of economic entities for the implementation of innovative projects, the UzVC National Venture Fund was established. Its goal is to create an infrastructure to support innovative ideas and startup ecosystems. So, in May 2021, the fund together with the Venture Investment Association of Uzbekistan held the first Central Asian Venture Forum in the capital. In addition to local venture funds, accelerators and participants in the innovation sphere, representatives of Russia, the USA, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan took part in the forum. As a result, memoranda of understanding were signed for the creation of joint funds and co-financing of startups. [3]

We would like to note that in order to support talented young people engaged in scientific activities in the regions, to involve them in science, to form prestigious scientific schools, to increase scientific potential, to finance scientific and startup projects, competitions "Academic Mobility" and "Future Scientist" with a prize fund of 50 billion soums have been announced. A permanent republican contest "The Third Renaissance - through the eyes of youth" has also been organized. At the final stage, the winner of each direction received 50 million soums for the implementation of the proposed initiatives.

The realization of the scientific and creative potential of the members of the Academy of Youth is supported and fully promotes. So, four platforms have been created: "Idea Generators", "Startups", "Business representatives", "Future academics". During the existence of the academy, six major competitions were organized for 35 billion soums, 115 projects were implemented, upon completion of which 567 jobs were created.[2]

Summarizing, we can conclude that science is the most important resource for the economic and social development of each state, guaranteeing citizens a decent standard of living, a democratic order of society organization, high standards of culture.

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